

Dissipative Structures and Self-organization Process in an Abstract Model of Neural Network

Giovanni Maria Guazzo ✉
Istituto Hull, Baronissi (SA), Italy

ABSTRACT:

This preliminary study shows an abstract model of the learning process; it will be identified as creating a dissipative structure and forming a self-organization process.

The dissipative structure will provoke a correlation within the whole system using the associated symmetry-breaking process.

Keywords: learning process, self-organization, dissipative structure, non-linear way.

Suggested Citation: G.M. Guazzo, "Dissipative Structures and Self-organization Process in an Abstract Model of Neural Network," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 2(2), pp. 17-21, Mar-Apr 2024. DOI: [10.59324/ejaset.2024.2\(2\).02](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejaset.2024.2(2).02)

INTRODUCTION

This work shows an abstract model of the learning process. The main property of the model is to define the concept of learning uniquely in each system.

Generally, the learning activity is considered a structural type of transaction triggered by using the appropriate external stimulus and associated with acquiring new patterns of behavior [1,2,3]. The first approach towards defining a system model that shows the learning process development fulfilling such a requirement date back to Hebb's work [4]. The main characteristics of Hebb's model, as regards our objective, maybe synthesized as follows:

- a. the behavior can be identified with the activity patterns of a neural network.
- b. the learning process consists of the variation of neuronic interconnection coefficients.
- c. the memory is the coefficient status at a given time.
- d. the values of such coefficients tend to be stable states depending on the network parameters and the nature of the external stimuli [5].

Some works [6,7,8] show that the attempts to construct an adequate model of the learning processes following Hebb's hypothesis clash very hard against mathematical problems. A possible solution to the problem can be found by using the continuous mathematical model of morphogenesis within the area of the self-organizing systems [9]. In this way, the learning process will no longer be considered as interconnection coefficient transactions but will be identified as the creating process of a dissipative structure.

The dissipative structure will provoke a correlation within the whole system using the associated symmetry-breaking process; this can be memory [9, 10, 11, 12, 13].

THE MODEL

The considerations of the previous section suggest imposing the condition that the model should describe, in some way, a correlation of one of the two variables representing the

components “activity” of the chosen system. Such a condition is compatible with the appearance of stable dissipative structures only within systems of the following type [14]:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\delta\alpha}{\delta t} = D_1 \frac{\delta^2\alpha}{\delta x^2} + \frac{1}{\pi}\beta\alpha + S \\ \frac{\delta\beta}{\delta t} = D_2 \frac{\delta^2\beta}{\delta x^2} r\alpha^2 + r\beta \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where D_1 , and D_2 are the diffusion coefficients of the variables α and β , r is an opportune parameter and S is a constant.

System (1) describes a self-organization process; therefore, a non-homogeneous dissipative structure will appear when some parameters overcome “thresholds”. The equilibrium points of such a system can be found by using a standard procedure [15]:

$$\alpha_0 = -\sqrt[3]{\pi S} \quad (2.a)$$

$$\beta_0 = \sqrt[3]{(\pi S)^2} \quad (2.b)$$

To analyze the stability of the equilibrium points, we must linearize system (1) in the neighbours of those points.

Therefore let [16]:

$$\alpha = \alpha_0 + \xi \quad (3.a)$$

$$\beta = \beta_0 + \eta \quad (3.b)$$

By replacing (3.a) and (3.b) in the system (1) and neglecting exponential terms of ξ , η overcoming the first order, we have:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\delta\xi}{\delta t} = D_1 \frac{\delta^2\xi}{\delta x^2} + \frac{\beta_0}{\pi}\xi + \frac{\alpha_0}{\pi}\eta \\ \frac{\delta\eta}{\delta t} = D_2 \frac{\delta^2\eta}{\delta x^2} + 2\alpha_0 r\xi - r\eta \end{cases} \quad 4)$$

If we assume now that the solution has the following form:

$$\xi = c_1 e^{\lambda t} \text{sen} kx \quad (5.a)$$

$$\eta = c_2 e^{\lambda t} \text{sen} kx \quad (5.b)$$

And we replace (5.a) and (5.b) within system (4), we have:

$$\begin{cases} \left(-K^2 D_1 - \lambda + \frac{\beta_0}{\pi}\right) C_1 + \frac{\alpha_0}{\pi} C_2 = 0 \\ 2\alpha_0 r C_1 + (-r - K^2 D_2 - \lambda) C_2 = 0 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

To have no null solutions in the system (6), the determinant of the system coefficient matrix must be equal to zero.

Then we have the relation:

$$\lambda^2 - \lambda \left(-K^2 D_1 + \frac{\beta_0}{\pi} - K^2 D_2 - r\right) + \left(-K^2 D_1 + \frac{\beta_0}{\pi}\right) (-r - K^2 D_2) + \frac{2\alpha^2 r}{\pi} = 0 \quad (7)$$

The solution of (7), considered as a λ -equation, is stable if both roots of λ have a negative real part. The critical point appears when either the known term is equal to zero or the coefficient of the λ -term is equal to zero.

Let us now suppose that one of the values of λ is positive and assume:

$$r - r_0 = \gamma_1 \varepsilon + \gamma_2 \varepsilon^2 \quad (8)$$

Where r_0 is the critical value of the parameter and ε is a small parameter.

Furthermore, let us assume that:

$$\xi = \varepsilon \xi_0 + \varepsilon^2 \xi_1 + \varepsilon^3 \xi_2 + \dots \quad (9.a)$$

$$\eta = \varepsilon \eta_0 + \varepsilon^2 \eta_1 + \varepsilon^3 \eta_2 + \dots \quad (9.b)$$

By replacing (8), (9.a) and (9.b) within the system (4) and making equal terms of the same order in ε , we obtain an infinite system of the equation of the following type:

$$\text{at } 1 - \text{st } \varepsilon - \text{order: } L_1(\xi, \eta) = Q_1(\xi, \eta) \quad (10.a)$$

$$\text{at } 2 - \text{st } \varepsilon - \text{order: } L_2(\xi, \eta) = Q_2(\xi, \eta) \quad (10.b)$$

$$\text{at } 3 - \text{st } \varepsilon - \text{order: } L_3(\xi, \eta) = Q_3(\xi, \eta) \quad (10.c)$$

If the operator $L_1(\xi, \eta)$ is equal to the system (4) with linear terms and $Q_1(\xi, \eta) = 0$, then it is possible by applying the Fredholm theorem, to impose the following condition of solvability:

$$\int_0^l (\xi_0 R_1 + \eta_0 R_2) dx = 0 \quad (11)$$

where l is the network length.

By developing the integral, where ξ_0 and η_0 are known, we have an equation in γ_1 .

If $\gamma_1 > 0$, then the dissipative structure is stable.

If $\gamma_1 < 0$, the dissipative structure is unstable.

Therefore, the dissipative structure form is:

$$\xi = \xi_0 + \left(\frac{r-r_0}{\gamma_1}\right) \xi_1 \quad (12.a)$$

$$\eta = \eta_0 + \left(\frac{r-r_0}{\gamma_1}\right) \eta_1 \quad (12.b)$$

where ξ_1 and η_1 are determined by resolving with approximation method the system of ε^2 – order.

If the system (1) does not depend on x , then it assumes the form:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\delta\alpha}{\delta t} = \frac{1}{\pi}\beta\alpha + S \\ \frac{\delta\beta}{\delta t} = r\alpha^2 + r\beta \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

Therefore, by deriving the first equation, we have:

$$\frac{\delta^2\alpha}{\delta t^2} - \frac{\pi}{\alpha^2} \left(\frac{\delta\alpha}{\delta t}\right)^2 + \left(-\frac{\pi S}{\alpha} + r\right) \frac{\delta\alpha}{\delta t} - \frac{r\alpha^3}{\pi} - \frac{\pi S^2}{\alpha^2} - rS + S^2 = 0 \quad (14)$$

By successive approximation of (14) for small new values of α and S , the dissipative structure is not stable at solution α_0 .

CONCLUSIONS

The results of section 2 show that, for critical values of the parameter, there is the conceiving of either temporal or spatial dissipative structure.

Therefore, for appropriate values of r , it is impossible to have a homogeneous network and then α and β assume the morphogenetic agent's rules. The network connectivity can be automatically determined from the dynamic evolution of α and β which privilege some distributions and remove others [7,17].

Moreover, from this model, it is possible to see that a learning process may exist only if the system is capable of a self-organization process, if the external intensity stimulus overcomes a given threshold and finally, if there are two types of internal activity, excitatory and inhibitory, mutually interacting in a non-linear way.

REFERENCES

1. E.R. Caianiello, "Outline of a theory of thought processes and thinking machines," *J. Theor. Biol.*, vol. 1, pp. 204-235, 1961. DOI: [10.1016/0022-5193\(61\)90046-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-5193(61)90046-7)
2. G.M. Guazzo, "Spontaneous formation of regions with different properties in neural nets," *BioSystems*, vol. 20, pp. 237-241, 1987. DOI: [10.1016/0303-2647\(87\)90031-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0303-2647(87)90031-1)

3. G.M. Guazzo, "A 'Systemic' Model of a mind-body interaction," *Eur. J. Theor. Appl. Sci.*, vol. 2(1), pp. 1-5, 2024. DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(1\).17](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(1).17)
4. D.O. Hebb, *The organization of Behavior*. New York: Wiley, 1949.
5. G.M. Guazzo, A 'morphogenetic' model of learning. *Chaos Solitons & Fractals*, vol. 3, pp. 257-263, 1993. DOI: [10.1016/0960-0779\(93\)90070-H](https://doi.org/10.1016/0960-0779(93)90070-H)
6. M.J. Feigenbaum, "Universal behaviour in nonlinear systems," *Physica*, vol. 7D, pp. 16-39, 1983. DOI: [10.1016/0167-2789\(83\)90112-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-2789(83)90112-4)
7. S. Grossberg, "Classical and instrumental learning by neuronal networks," In R. Rosen & F. Snell (Eds.). *Progress in Theoretical Biology* (Vol. 3). New York: Academic Press, 1974.
8. M.A. Cohen, S. Grossberg, "Absolute stability of global pattern formation and parallel memory storage by competitive neural networks," *IEEE Transactions on System, Man and Cybernetics*, vol. 13, pp. 815-823, 1983. DOI: [10.1109/TSMC.1983.6313075](https://doi.org/10.1109/TSMC.1983.6313075)
9. G.M. Guazzo, "Dissipative structures emerging within an abstract model of neural network," in E.R. Caianiello (Ed.), *Physics of cognitive processes* (pp. 163-170). Singapore: World Scientific Publishing Co., 1987.
10. G.B. Ermentrout, J.D. Cowan, "Secondary bifurcation in neuronal nets," *SIAM J. Appl. Math.*, vol. 12, pp. 323-340, 1980. DOI: [10.1137/0139028](https://doi.org/10.1137/0139028)
11. G.B. Ermentrout, J.D. Cowan, "Large scale spatially organized activity in neural nets," *SIAM J. Appl. Math.*, vol. 38, pp. 1-21, 1980. DOI: [10.1137/0138001](https://doi.org/10.1137/0138001)
12. S.M. Oosovets, et al. "Electrical activity of the brain: mechanisms and interpretation," *Soviet Physics Uspekhi*, vol. 24, pp. 801-828, 1983.
13. L.M. Ricciardi, H. Umezawa, "Brain and physics of many-body problems," *Kibernetik*, 1, 443-469, 1978. DOI: [10.1007/BF00292170](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00292170)
14. B.N. Belintsev, "Dissipative structures and the problem of biological pattern formation," *Soviet Physics Uspekhi*, vol. 26, pp. 775-800, 1983. DOI: [10.1070/PU1983v026n09ABEH004492](https://doi.org/10.1070/PU1983v026n09ABEH004492)
15. J.F.G. Auchmuty, G. Nicolis, "Bifurcation analysis of nonlinear reaction-diffusion equations. I: Evolution equations and steadystate solutions," *Bull. Math. Biol.*, vol. 37, pp. 325-365, 1975. DOI: [10.1007/BF02462929](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02462929)
16. E. Pessa, "Un nuovo modello matematico del processo di apprendimento di Grossberg," *Comunicazioni Scientifiche di psicologia generale*, vol. 11, pp. 105-146, 1983.
17. S. Grossberg, "How does a brain build a cognitive code?" *Psycholog. Rev.*, vol. 58, pp. 1-51, 1980. DOI: [10.1037/0033-295X.87.1.1](https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-295X.87.1.1)

